
PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING AND ANTIDIABETIC PROPERTIES OF *Musa acuminata*
ETHANOLIC FRUIT EXTRACT ON ALLOXAN INDUCED DIABETIC ALBINO RATS

¹Okon, J. E., ¹Esenowo, G. J., and ¹Utuk, K. E.

¹Department of Botany and Ecological Studies, University of Uyo, P. M. B. 1017, Uyo. Akwa Ibom State
Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The hypoglycaemic effect of *Musa acuminata* ethanolic fruit extract was examined using alloxan-induced diabetic rats. The rats were divided into 5 groups of rats each. All the groups were induced with diabetes and treated with different doses of the plant extract, i.e. 500, 1000 and 1500 mg/kg (low, middle and high dose respectively), which was administered orally for a period of 24 hours. The last group served as a positive group, treated with 1.2 mg/kg glibenclamide (standard drug). The plant was observed to have hypoglycemic effect on each group of diabetic rats as it reduced their fasting blood sugar (FBS) level from 232.7 ± 167.5 to 201.7 ± 138.0 mg/dl (group III), 278.7 ± 172.5 to 260 ± 246.8 mg/dl (group IV) and 319 ± 196.8 to 112.7 ± 25.6 mg/dl (group V), when compared with the negative control 393 ± 1.41 and 444 ± 31.1 mg/dl at 3 hours (group I). There was a significant (P < 0.05) reduction between the control and the treated groups which was in dose dependent manner. The results showed that *Musa acuminata* extract had significant anti-diabetic activity which has laid credence that it is a hypoglycemic agent. Phytochemical screening of the fruit extract of *Musa acuminata* revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids, terpenes, anthraquinones, and cardiac glycosides. The extract had no adverse effect when administered intraperitoneally on normal mice. These findings suggest that ethanolic extract of *Musa acuminata* fruit possesses anti-hyperglycemic properties which justified the traditional use of the fruit in the treatment of Diabetes.

KEYWORDS: *Musa acuminata*, hypoglycaemic potentials, Diabetes mellitus, phytochemical, glibenclamide, alloxan, extract.

Received for Publication: 11/03/13

Accepted for Publication: 08/05/13

Corresponding Author: joesplendid@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Musa acuminata, bluggoe plantain banana are perennial herbs. The trunk (known as pseudostem) is made of tightly packed layers of leaf sheaths emerging from completely, or partially buried corms (Simmonds, 1962). The inflorescence of *Musa acuminata* grows horizontally or obliquely from the trunk. The individual flowers are white to yellowish-white, and are negatively geotropic (growing upwards and away from the ground)

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournal.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

(Markku *et al.*, 2001). Both male and female flowers are present in a single inflorescence. Female flowers located near the base (and develop into fruit) and the male flowers located at the tipmost top-shaped bud in between leathery bracts. The rather slender fruits are berries; the size of each depends on the number of seeds they contain. Each fruit can have 15 to 62 seeds. Each fruit bunch can have an average of 161.76 ± 60.62 fingers with each finger around 2.4cm (0.94 inches) by 9 cm in size (Dokrak *et al.*, 2010). The seeds of *Musa acuminata* are around 5-6mm in diameter. They are sub-globose or angular in shape and very hard. The tiny embryo is located at the end of the micropyle (Simmonds, 1962). The traditional medicine practitioners are using the fruit to treat diabetes. This information is scanty and not well documented. Hence, this research aims to study its efficacy of its use for treatment of Diabetes by traditional medicine practitioners in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

This study was carried out in Pharmacognosy laboratories (I and II) in University of Uyo, Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State-Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State is situated between latitudes $4^{\circ} 31'$ and $5^{\circ} 30'N$ and Longitude $7^{\circ} 31'$ and $8^{\circ} 20'E$ with a total land area of about 8,412km². The topography is plain, and surrounding lands are cultivated. This area has two seasons that is the wet and dry season. The wet season occurs between May and October, while the dry season occurs between November and April. Rainfall ranges about 3000 mm along the coast at a heavy downpour and decrease to 2000 mm on the North fringe. The relative humidity of this area is high and ranges between 75% and 85%.

Collection and Identification of Plant Material

The fruits of *Musa acuminata* were collected from Ibiaku Itam in Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State on August, 2012. The plant was identified and authenticated by Dr. (Mrs.) M. E. Bassey, a plant taxonomist in the Department of Botany and Ecological studies, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Preparation of Plant Extract

The *Musa acuminata* fruit samples were peeled, shed dried and pulverized to powder form and was macerated with 1000ml of 70% ethanol for 72hrs. The solution was filtered using glass funnel packed with cotton wool. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness by heating in a water bath at 40°C to give a yield of 58g of semi-dry extract with brownish colour. This was reconstituted in distilled water to an appropriate concentration for administration and phytochemical screening.

Collection and Maintenance of Animals

Twenty five (25) healthy male and female sex albino rats weighing 150 – 250 g were obtained from the animal house of the Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Uyo, Uyo and maintained according to the guidelines of Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Phytochemical Screening

The experiment was carried out in the Department of Pharmacognosy and Natural Medicine, University of Uyo, Uyo. The phytochemical screening involves the simple chemical test to detect the presence of secondary metabolites. The methods of Trease and Evans (2009) were used for phytochemical screening.

Determination of Median Lethal Dose (LD₅₀)

Thirty (30) Swiss albino mice weighing 25-32 g were dose by the intraperitoneal (i.p.) route using the method of Lorke (1983). The animals were administered with 5000 mg/kg, 4000 mg/kg, 3000 mg/kg, 2000 mg/kg, 1000 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg of *Musa acuminata* fruit extract in 5 groups of 5 mice each. The animals were observed for manifestation of physical signs of toxicity and the number of death within 24 hours was recorded. The LD₅₀ was calculated as the geometric mean of the maximum dose producing 0% mortality and the minimum dose producing 100% mortality. Food was withdrawn for 18 hrs before the onset of the experiment according to methods of Amresh *et al.* (2008).

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{D_0 \times D_{100}}$$

Where: D₀ = Maximum dose producing 0% mortality
D₁₀₀ = Minimum dose producing 100% mortality

Induction of Diabetes

Male Wistar Albino rats were made diabetic by a single dose of intraperitoneal injection of 150 mg/kg body weight of alloxan monohydrate in sterile normal saline. The rats were maintained on 5% glucose solution for next 24 hours to prevent hypoglycaemia. Four days later, blood samples were drawn from tail vein and glucose levels were determined to confirm the development of diabetes (Kim *et al.*, 2006).

Experimental Design

Alloxan Induced Diabetic Rats:

Aqueous extracts of fruits of *Musa acuminata* (10 mg/ml) was orally administered to the diabetic rats at a dose of 100mg/kg after determining their initial fasting blood glucose concentration. The blood glucose concentration was then assayed at one hour interval for five hours (5hrs). Distilled water was administered in place of the extract for the control studies. A standard anti-diabetic drug (Glibenclamide 0.5 mg/ml) was similarly administered to the diabetic rats, blood glucose concentration determined at the same interval for the same duration.

The diabetic rats were divided into five groups of 5 rats each and treated as follows:

- Group I: Diabetic rats administered with 500 mg/kg of extract of *Musa acuminata*.
- Group II: Diabetic rats administered with 1000 mg/kg of fruit extract of *Musa acuminata*.
- Group III: Diabetic rats treated orally with 1500 mg/kg of *Musa acuminata* fruit extract
- Group IV: Diabetic rats treated orally with 1.2 mg/kg of Glibenclamide.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Group V: Diabetic rats given 10 ml/kg of distilled water (Control).

For acute study, the fasting blood glucose level was monitored after 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 24 hours of administration of the extract. The blood samples were collected through the tail vein just prior to and on the time frames after drug treatment. The oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) was performed for dose of aqueous fruit extract of *Musa acuminata* and blood glucose level was measured by one touch glycometer (accu-check). The glucose level was measured at the interval of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 24 hours after the administration of the extracts.

Statistical analysis

This was carried out using windows Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 17.0. One way analysis of variance was adopted for comparison, and the results were subject to Student's t-test using least square deviation (LSD). The data were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard error. $P < 0.05$ were considered significant.

RESULTS

The results of phytochemical screening investigated from the fruit extract of *Musa acuminata* revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, terpenes, flavonoids, anthraquinones and cardiac glycosides (Table I). The mice treated through intraperitoneal (i.p.) route with a single dose of 500-5000 mg/kg of fruit extract showed decrease in writhing, respiration distress, decreased limb and no death was recorded with 24 hours post administration of the extract, since the extract is non-toxic, the LD₅₀ was taken to be 5000 mg/kg.

The mean glucose concentration of controlled and ethanolic fruit extract of *Musa acuminata* treated rats on 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 24 hours are in Table 2. Intraperitoneal administration of Alloxan monohydrate into the rats caused significant diabetogenic response in albino rats with significant increase in the levels of blood sugar as compared with the normal control rats. The blood glucose level was increased from 393 - 511.5mg/dl (Table 2). Following oral administration of the extract at the dose of 1500 mg/kg, the blood glucose level (BGL) was significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced. Meanwhile, the dose at 500 mg/kg and 1000 mg/kg also had significant effect on the Blood glucose level as compared to the diabetic untreated rats. The data obtained at 1500 mg/kg compared favourably well with that of glibenclamide (standard drug) treated group (30.9 ± 181.8 mg/dl) at 24 hours (Table 2). However, the effect of the extract at high dose was less than that of the standard drug.

All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Table 1: Phytochemical screening result of *Musaacuminata* fruit extract

Test	Inference
Alkaloids	
Dragendorff's reagent	++
Mayer's reagent	++
Picric acid	++
Saponins	
Frothing test	++
Anthraquinones	
Borntrager's test	+++
Cardiac glycosides	
Salkowski Test	+++
Terpenes	
Flavonoids	
Shinoda reduction test	+++
Tannins	
Ferric chloride test	+++

Key:

+++	-	Abundance
++	-	Moderate
+	-	Trace
-	-	Absent

Table 2: Anti-diabetic Effect of Ethanolic Extract of *Musa acuminata* on Blood Glucose level of Alloxan-induced diabetic rats

Groups	Mg/kg Treatment	Blood Glucose Level mg/dl						
		Hrs → 0	1	2	3	4	5	24
I	-ve control (Distilled water 10ml/kg)	393±1.41	417±45.3	398.5±37.5	444±31.1	412±39.6	511.5±79.90	382±66.5
II	+ve control (1.2mg/kg Glibenclamide)	301.7±153.5	281.3±200.4	269.3±181.8	284.7±193.3	282±197.5	274.3±188.3	309±181.8
III	500mg/kg (Low dose)	232.7±167.5*	250.3±219.7	195.3±141.0*	227±182.7*	236.7±203.8*	216.3±175.5	201.7±138.0*
IV	1000mg/kg (Middle dose)	278.7±172.5*	216±177.8	219.3±154.4	198.3±159.1*	209.3±184.2*	228±173.9*	260±246.8
V	1500mg/kg (High dose)	319±196.8	264.3±146.0	241±139.7	244.3±121.0*	218.3±97.1	199.3±105.6	112.7±25.6*

Data are processed and expressed as mean values ± standard error of mean. *Significant (P<0.05) when compared with the control group (n=5)

DISCUSSION

The results of this work showed that *Musa acuminata* fruits extract are abundant in flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, terpenes and anthraquinones. In accordance with these results, Shamaet *al.* (2010) worked on *Ficus glomerata* in alloxan induced diabetic rats and reported that the plant extract have antioxidant potential. Presence of flavonoids and tannins in the extract is known to possess anti-diabetic activity. In the present investigation, the observed antidiabetic potential of test extract may also be due to the presence of similar phytoconstituents which were evident by phytochemical screening, and also due to the reported antioxidant potential of the titled plant.

According to this study, the extract of *Musa acuminata* fruits caused antihyperglycaemic effect by promoting regeneration of β -cells or by promoting these cells from destruction by restricting glucose load as well as by promoting unrestricted endogenous insulin action. Similarly, Jadhav *et al.* (2009) stated that antihyperglycaemic effect may also be caused by the effect of plant extract (*Diospyros melanoxylon*) on β -cells to release insulin or activate the insulin receptors, to absorb the blood sugar and stimulate the peripheral glucose consumption. In addition, Ji *et al.* (2006) who worked in Korean medicinal plant reported that hypoglycemic effect may be due to depression of key gluconeogenic or the increase in the levels of glucose transport and stimulation of uptake in peripheral tissues. Another effect of the plant extract may be that it preserves the cells of islets of Langerhans of β -cells function, which results in a significant increase in insulin activity (Soon and Tan, 2002 and Kamiya *et al.*, 2008). Hence, *Musa acuminata* extract had hypoglycaemic effect on the normal rats and should be monitored to know when they fall below normal glycaemia. The potent and progressive reduction activity of blood glucose level of the extract with pretreatment and treatment values confirms the antidiabetic potential of *Musa acuminata* fruits.

CONCLUSION

From the data obtained, it could be concluded that the ethanolic fruit extract of *Musa acuminata* fruit possesses anti-hyperglycaemic properties which confirmed the traditional use of *Musa acuminata* fruits by traditional medicine practitioners for treatment of diabetes. Based on the findings from this research work, further investigations are necessary to: carry out further experimental investigation needed to exploit its relevant therapeutic effect to substantiate its ethnomedicinal usage of the plant and should be cultivated commercially and consumed as a dieting menu for hyperglycaemic patients.

REFERENCES

- Amresh, G., Paras, N. S. and Chandana, V. A. (2008). Toxicological screening of traditional medicine of Laghupatha (*Cissampelos parviflora*) in experimental animals. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 116: 454-460.
- Dokrak, M., Piya, P., Prateep, D. and Tanaka, H. (2010). "The role of Wild Banana (*Musa acuminata* colla) on Wildlife Diversity in mixed Deciduous Forest, Kanchanaburi Province, Western Thailand". *Bioscience Kasetsart, J.* (Kasetsart University). 44(1):35-43.
- Jadhav, J. K., Masirkar, V. J. and Deshmukh, V. N. (2009). Antihyperglycaemic effect of *Diospyros melanoxylon* (Roxb.) bark against Alloxan-Induced Diabetic rats. *Inter. J. Pharm. Tech. Res.*, 1:196-200.
- Ji, S. K., Jung, B. J., Chang, W. C. and Sei, C. K. (2006). Hypoglycaemic and Antihyperlipidemic Effect of Four Korean Medicinal Plants in Alloxan Induced Diabetic Rats. *Amer. J. Biochem. Biotechnol.*, 2(4): 154-160.
- Kamiya, K., Hamabe, W., Harade, S., Murakami, R., Tokuyama, S. and Satake, T. (2008). Chemical constituents of *Morinda Citrifolia* roots exhibits hypoglycaemic effects in streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic mice. *Biol. Pharm. Bull.* 31(5): 935-938.
- Kim, H. K., Kim, M. J., Cho, H. Y., Kim, E. K. and Shin, D. H. (2006). Antioxidant and antidiabetic effects of amaranth (*Amaranthus esculantus*) in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Cell Biochem. Funct.*, 24: 195-199.
- Lorke, D. (1983). A new approach to practical acute toxicity test, *Arch. Toxicol.*, 54: 275-286.

Markku, H. and Edmond, D. (2001). *Musa acuminata* in Northern Borneo. International Network for the improvement of Banana and plantain (INIBAP) <http://bananas.diversityinternational.org/files/pdf/publication/reportborner.pdf>. Retrieved June 11, 2011.

Sharma, V. K., Rumar, S., Patel, H. J. and Hugar, S. (2010). Hypoglycaemic activity of *Ficus glomerata* in alloxan induced diabetic rats, *Intern. J. Pharmaceut. Sci. Review and Res.*, 1:18-22.

Simmonds, N. W. (1962). "Where our bananas come from" *New Scientist (Read Business Information).Sci.*, 16(307): 36-39.

Soon, Y. Y. and Tan B. K. H. (2002). Evaluation of the Hypoglycaemic and Anti-Oxidant Activities of *Morinda Officinalis* in Streptozotocin Induced Diabetic Rats. *Singap. Med. J.*, 43(2):77-85.

Trease, G. E. and Evans, W. O. (2009). Trease and Evans *Pharmacognosy*, Sixteenth Edition. New York: Sauder's Elsevier Limited. Pp.104-262.
